

A SURVEY TO IDENTIFY OPERATIONAL WELFARE INDICATORS (OWIs) IN FARMED EUROPEAN SEA BASS *Dicentrarchus labrax* AND GILTHEAD SEA BREAM *Sparus aurata*

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Introduction

Welfare of farmed fish is a key aspect of sustainable and ethical aquaculture. At European level, the EU Commission has recently published studies on welfare of farmed fish and has reported on fish welfare during transport and at slaughter to the EU Council and Parliament (SANTE, 2017; SCAR FISH, 2018; COM 87 final (2018)). The European Aquaculture Advisory Council has adopted in 2017 the position paper ‘Farmed Fish Welfare During Slaughter in the European Union’ and in June 2019 has provided a new recommendation for optimising fish welfare at slaughter (AAC, 2019). Producers’ Associations, certification bodies and NGOs are searching for suitable operational welfare indicators (OWIs) for measuring the welfare status of farmed fish and improving standard and welfare friendly practices.

The PerformFISH consortium (<http://performfish.eu/>) is working on welfare of European sea bass and gilthead sea bream and is validating a set of OWIs and a welfare scoring system specifically designed for sea bass and sea bream, in collaboration with fish Producers’ Associations and Mediterranean aquaculture companies. This paper presents the results of the PerformFISH *Fish Welfare Survey* for the selection of most suitable OWIs for sea bass and sea bream aquaculture.

Materials and Methods

The PerformFISH consortium has adopted in 2017 a first set of Welfare key performance indicators actually in use by 20 farm companies participating in the benchmarking of performances of sea bass and sea bream across the Mediterranean area. The welfare indicators are: i) total fish mortalities; ii-iii) fish mortalities after 3 and 10 days after transport and stocking; iv) vaccinated fish by disease; v-vi) number of antiparasitic and antibiotic treatments; vii) fish feed intake; viii) fish stocking density; ix) number of oxygen depletion persistence days

The *Fish Welfare Survey* was designed to identify additional OWIs for sea bass and sea bream to be used during grow-out farming in sea cages and land-based tanks, transport and at slaughter. The set of OWIs was chosen following an analysis and systematization of knowledge on welfare of sea bass and sea bream available in literature. About four hundred scientific publications were consulted, together with OIE and EU recommendations, EFSA opinions, Technical guidelines and Codes of conduct (FAO, FEAP), Benchmarking systems (GAPI, GSSI), Certification schemes (RSPCA, ASC, Global GAP, BAP GAA, FOS, Organic), Welfare Handbook for Atlantic salmon (Noble et al., 2018) and expert judgments. The approaches to assess animal welfare in terrestrial livestock production (e.g. Welfare Quality; AWIN) have been further considered.

The PerformFISH consortium (Scientific partners, Producers’ Associations, Industry) participating in the *Fish Welfare Survey* is requested to score the suitability of OWIs on the basis of the following indicator’s attributes: informative, reliable, cost and labour effective, repeatable, comparable and easy to apply.

Results

The 48 OWIs included in the survey cover 9 different areas of fish welfare: health, growth, behavior, housing, transport, harvest, stunning/slaughter, staff training and compliance with recommendations (OIE and EU). The overall set of OWIs includes a 46% of animal-based indicators and a 54% of indirect indicators related to environment and husbandry management and practices. The 47% of OWIs are quantitative indicators providing numerical values for welfare scoring and 53% are qualitative indicators reporting on the use of best management practices during farming, transport and slaughter. Although most OWIs proposed in PerformFISH survey are included in aquaculture certification schemes, only few quantitative indicators are available for farmed sea bass and sea bream.

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Discussion and conclusion

Although the general aspects of health and the welfare of farmed fish are well known by farm managers, a set of suitable OWIs for analyze welfare status of sea bass and sea bream is still missing and reference values for most of quantitative indicators are completely lacking. A Welfare Scoring System based on OWIs can thus improve the measurement and certification of fish welfare status. The set of OWIs will be a simple and friendly tool for farmers and health managers to measure fish welfare, helping them to find room for improvement in husbandry practices. Welfare indicators will be further used to inform retailers, consumers, NGOs and policy makers on welfare-friendly farming practices and standards in use in marine fish farming secto .

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